

On the Vapour Pressure and Chemical Constant of Formaldehyde.

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In course of investigations now in progress on the study of the reactions

it was found necessary to investigate the physical properties of pure formaldehyde in order that the conditions of equilibrium governing the above reactions might be theoretically ascertained. The Nernst Heat theorem could be applied to the above reactions, if the Chemical Constant of pure formaldehyde and its latent heat of vaporisation at various temperatures could be found out,—the corresponding data for the other molecular species taking part in the reactions being already known.

Preparation of Pure Liquid Formaldehyde.

Gaseous formaldehyde is an extremely fugitive substance ; it becomes very easily transformed into solid paraform and various other solid polymerisation products. Kekule¹ succeeded in obtaining liquid formaldehyde by heating dry paraform and condensing the gas produced.

¹ Ber. 1892, 25, 2435.

Various methods were tried for preparing pure formaldehyde vapour—the one recommended by Sachs¹ which consisted in heating oxymethyl-phthalimide appeared promising. But it was ultimately found that consistent data on the physical properties of formaldehyde could only be had when formaldehyde was obtained from paraform which had been thoroughly dried by anhydrous phosphorous pentoxide. Even then it was found that if the temperature of liquid formaldehyde were raised above -30°C , transformation into solid polymerisation products became very rapid, and the results became untrustworthy; below -30°C however, the liquid keeps unchanged indefinitely.

Fig. 1 gives the experimental arrangement for collecting pure liquid formaldehyde in the experimental tube.

A—Phosphorous pentoxide tube plugged with glass wool.

B—Paraform (Kahlbaum's purest) tube protected by an asbestos mantle.

C—Experimental tube dipped in liquid air contained in a Dewar flask.

M—Manometer U tube, the bent portion of which is filled with mercury.

E—The point where formaldehyde condensed.

F and G—for connection to vacuum pump.

The whole apparatus was evacuated, stopcock G closed and F sealed, and paraform was allowed to dry in vacuum for a fortnight. Paraform in B was then heated and dry formaldehyde was condensed at E by means of liquid air. Care should be taken that the end of the delivery tube at E does not get choked with solid formaldehyde. After sufficient formaldehyde had collected, the experimental tube was sealed off at D.

¹ Ber. 1899, 31, 1231.

*Measurement of Vapour Pressure of Liquid
Formaldehyde.*

As has been observed before, formaldehyde vapour begins to condense as a solid whose vapour pressure is almost zero at temperatures above -30°C . This unique behaviour makes it necessary to have a pressure-recording device which could be maintained at temperatures below -30°C . Otherwise a part of the vapour will condense as solid in the measuring instrument, where the pressure will necessarily fall, and a gradient of pressure will thus be established from the surface of the liquid to the point where the pressure is being recorded. To obviate this difficulty, a thin glass tube M was attached to the experimental tube C, and was bent close to its sides in the form of U. The mercury column at M remained dipped in the liquid of thermostat where the temperature did not exceed -30°C , but was not below about -35°C , and hence during the measurement of pressure no solid paraform could condense on the surface of the mercury in M. The experimental arrangements are given in Fig. 2.

T is a wide Dewar flask about four-fifths filled with liquid air. T' is another unsilvered Dewar flask dipped in T with a side tube at the top, which by means of a Vollmer pump, creates a vacuum variable at will, in the annular space. For very low temperatures, a good vacuum is essential. It contained pure acetone up to the top in which dipped the experimental tube containing liquid formaldehyde.

Stirrer.—The stirrer consisted of a thick tube of copper attached to the end of two stout iron wires. At the bottom of the tube were attached several fine copper filaments at right angles, to help agitation. It was moved up and down about 10 cms. from the bottom by means of an eccentric pulley run by a hot air motor.

Heating Coil.—Round the copper tube of the stirrer, as near to the bottom as possible, was wound a heating coil of silk-covered constantan wire insulated by means of thin mica. The leads passed up along the stout iron wires of the stirrer and ended in the terminals of a storage battery. Current from the battery was regulated by a rheostat, and thus the thermostat liquid could be heated up to any desired temperature.

Temperature Gradient in the Thermostat Liquid.

The temperature is lowest at the bottom, and is highest at the top, due to contact with air of the room. Due to the movement of the copper cylinder stirrer, the temperature within about 8 cms. from the bottom remains constant. Beyond that, the temperature gradually rises, and this rise becomes very rapid as the level of liquid air in the outer flask T is passed. In the region of M, the temperature could, with a certain amount of manipulation be maintained constant at about -30°C .

Thermocouple.—A copper constantan couple was used, the electromotive force being given by the Nernst formula

$$E = 31 \cdot 32T \log \left(1 + \frac{T}{90} \right) + 1 \times 10^{-7} T^4$$

$$\text{or } E - E_1 = 31 \cdot 32T \log \left(1 + \frac{T}{90} \right) + 1 \times 10^{-7} T^4 - 31 \cdot 32T_1 \log \left(1 + \frac{T_1}{90} \right) + 1 \times 10^{-7} T_1^4$$

where if T is the absolute temperature of the hot junction (that of ice-bath), the cold junction being at *absolute zero*, E is the E. M. F. in microvolts; T_1 , the temperature of liquid air thermostat and the difference $E - E_1$ is the E. M. F. actually observed between the thermostat temperature and the ice-bath outside. The cold junction was near at the bottom of the thermostat close to the side of the experimental tube where a few cc. of liquid formaldehyde was present. The couple had been previously

used to measure the temperature of melting mercury and the temperature was found to be -38.6°C .

D—The experimental tube C after immersion in the thermostat which had already attained constant temperature, was broken open at D and connected to a high vacuum pump which chased away the last trace of air, and then closed. To prevent the displacement of the mercury column during the evacuation the manometer M was connected to a pump and evacuated simultaneously.

Reservoir.—R. Pressure of air in this reservoir was rendered equal to that of liquid formaldehyde—the equality being indicated by the mercury column in M. This was done by decreasing the pressure in the reservoir by evacuation through the side tube S₁ and then increasing by carefully opening and closing stopcocks H₁ and H₂ joined together by a capillary tubing.

P—Manometer connected to air reservoir; the difference in the levels of the mercury columns was measured by means of a kathetometer.

Experimental Results and Discussion.

The vapour pressure of formaldehyde at various temperatures are given below

-91°C	1.00 cm.
$-55^{\circ}.5\text{C}$	14.25 cms.
$-46^{\circ}.8\text{C}$	23.7 cms.
$-41^{\circ}.8\text{C}$	30.45 cms.
$-34^{\circ}.5\text{C}$	41.4 cms.

According to Nernsts' simplified equation, the vapour pressure of a liquid can be expressed by an equation of the type

$$\ln p = -\frac{\lambda_0}{RT} + \frac{3.5}{R} \ln T - \frac{c}{R} T + (i + \ln R)$$

$$\text{or } \log p = -\frac{\lambda_0}{2 \cdot 3RT} + \frac{3 \cdot 5}{R} \log T - \frac{\epsilon T}{2 \cdot 3R} + C$$

where C is the Chemical Constant of the liquid. The experimental data recorded above agree with the equation

$$\log p = -\frac{6500}{4 \cdot 6T} + 1 \cdot 75 \log T - \frac{0 \cdot 035 T}{4 \cdot 6} + 3 \cdot 3$$

where P is expressed in atmospheres and the heat energy in calories. The latent heat of evaporation at absolute zero is 6500 and the chemical constant = 3.3. It is obvious that an equation containing three unknown constants λ_0 , ϵ and C can undergo a good deal of relative variation in the values of these constants without greatly affecting the values of P, and hence their values fixed as above cannot be very accurate. If, however, ϵ is determined independently from measurements of specific heat, the equation would only contain two unknown variables λ_0 and C and their values could be fixed from measurements of P without much uncertainty. Measurement of specific heat of formaldehyde is in progress and the value of C given above is only tentative. It is to be noted that the Chemical Constant of formaldehyde (3.3) is identical with that of ether, and slightly less than that of acetone (3.7), but very much less than that of ethyl alcohol 4.1.

Troutons' Law.—The boiling point of formaldehyde was approximately -21°C . From the Nernst formula (Wärmesatz, p. 125)

$$\lambda = (\lambda_0 + 3 \cdot 5T - \epsilon T^2) \left(1 - \frac{p}{\pi_0} \right)$$

where p is the pressure at the temperature at which λ is to be calculated and π_0 the critical pressure,

Neglecting $\frac{p}{\pi_0}$ compared to unity, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda &= 6500 + 3 \cdot 5 \times 252 - 0 \cdot 035 \times (252)^2 \\ &= 5160 \text{ calories.}\end{aligned}$$

Applying Troutons' Rule, we have $\frac{\lambda}{T} = \frac{5160}{252} = 20 \cdot 5$ units of entropy.

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